

Cd^{II}-azido and -thiocyanato complexes of *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- α (or β)-aminonaphthalene

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Abstract : Azido or thiocyanato bridged Cd^{II} complexes of *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- α (or β)-aminonaphthalene (α - or β -NaiPy) are synthesized and characterized by spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, emission, FT-IR and ¹H NMR). The single crystal X-ray structure of [Cd(*N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- β -aminonaphthalene)(SCN)₂]_n (4) has revealed thiocyanato bridged 2-D polymer. Examination of luminescence activity of the complexes suggests that the complexes are highly emissive and have reasonably good life.

Keywords : Naphthyl Schiff base, Cd^{II} complex, 2-D polymer, fluorescent, X-ray structure, DFT calculation.

Introduction

Schiff bases are extensively used for the studies of the complexes of transition metal ions for many years because of many potential applications¹⁻⁴. Recent years have witnessed a great deal of interest in the synthesis of heterocyclic Schiff bases containing diimine (-N=C-C=N-) chelating function⁵⁻⁹. The number of heteroatoms, ring size and the nature of substituents in the heterocyclic ring significantly modify and regulate the physical, photo-physical, chemical, catalytic, redox, biological etc. properties of the compounds¹⁰. 2,2'-Bipyridine (bpy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) are legendary heterocycles in the development of diimine chemistry of metal complexes⁷⁻¹¹. The key feature of them is their π -acidity. The condensation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde with aromatic amine has synthesized a molecule, in which in-built C=N in pyridine ring is conjugated with exocyclic C=N group¹²⁻¹⁴. The reports on the Schiff bases obtained from pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and naphthylamine are known very recently¹⁵⁻²⁰. In this article we wish to report synthesis and spectral characterization of cadmium(II)-N₃⁻/SCN⁻ complexes of *N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- α (or β)-aminonaphthalene (α - or β -NaiPy). The structural confirmation of the complexes in one case has been carried out by single crystal X-ray diffraction data.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

α -Naphthylamine and β -naphthylamine were purchased from Thomas Baker & Co. Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde was purchased from Lancaster Ltd., England. The organic solvents were purified and dried by standard methods²¹. α/β -*N*-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]- α (or β)-aminonaphthalene (α - or β -NaiPy) were synthesized by equimolar condensation of pyridine 2-carboxaldehyde and α - or β -naphthylamine in ethanol following the reported procedure¹⁵. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality and were used as received.

UV-Vis spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and infrared spectra were obtained from Perkin-Elmer Spectrum RX1 instrument. Microanalyses were collected from Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyser. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded from Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR. Solution electrical conductivity was measured in Systronics 305 digital conductivity meter. Luminescence property was measured using Perkin-Elmer LS 55 fluorescence spectrophotometer at room temperature (298 K) in DMF solution by 1 cm path length quartz cell.

The fluorescence quantum yield of the cadmium(II) complexes was determined using carbazole laser dye as a

reference with a known ϕ_R of 0.42 in DMF²². The complex as well as reference was excited at 331 nm for **3** and **5**, and 341 for **4** and **6**, maintaining nearly equal absorbance (~ 0.1), and the emission spectra were recorded from 345 to 600 nm. The area of the emission spectrum was integrated using the software available in the instrument and the quantum yield was calculated according to the following equation :

$$\phi_S/\phi_R = [A_S/A_R] \times [(Abs)_R/(Abs)_S] \times [\eta_S^2/\eta_R^2]$$

Here, ϕ_S and ϕ_R are the fluorescence quantum yield of the sample and reference, respectively. A_S and A_R are the area under the fluorescence spectra of the sample and the reference respectively, $(Abs)_S$ and $(Abs)_R$ are the respective optical densities of the sample and the reference solution at the wavelength of excitation, and η_S and η_R are the values of refractive index for the respective solvent used for the sample and reference.

Fluorescence lifetimes were measured using a time-resolved spectrofluorometer from IBH, UK. The instrument uses a picosecond diode laser (NanoLed-07, 408 nm) as the excitation source and works on the principle of time-correlated single photon counting. The instrument responses function is ~ 230 ps at FWHM. To eliminate depolarization effects on the fluorescence decays, measurements were done with magic angle geometry (54.7°) for the excitation and emission polarizers. The observed decays of $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]$ (**3**) fits with single exponential decay and $[Cd(\beta\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]$ (**4**), $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(N_3)_2]$ (**5**) and $[Cd(\beta\text{-NaiPy})(N_3)_2]$ (**6**) match properly with bi-exponential decay profile.

*Synthesis of bis-thiocyanato-(N-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- α -aminonaphthalene)cadmium(II), $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]$ (**3**) :*

N-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]- α -aminonaphthalene (**1**) (98.3 mg, 0.42 mmol) in MeOH (10 ml) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution (15 ml) of $Cd(OAc)_2$ (109.5 mg, 0.41 mmol) at room temperature and stirred for 1 h. To the yellow solution, 10 ml methanolic solution of NH_4SCN (63.2 mg, 0.83 mmol) was added dropwise under stirring condition and the stirring was continued for another 2.5 h. The colour turned to yellowish brown. Upon slow evaporation of the solvent, yellowish brown coloured product was left. It was then washed with 1 : 1 methanol, water and dried over $CaCl_2$ desiccator. The yield was 133.1 mg (68%).

The β -complex was prepared similarly. The yield was 70%. Microanalytical data : Anal. Calcd. $C_{18}H_{12}N_4S_2Cd$

(**3**) : C, 46.91; H, 2.61; N, 12.16. Found : C, 47.06; H, 2.66; N, 12.24%. $C_{18}H_{12}N_4S_2Cd$ (**4**) : C, 46.91; H, 2.61; N, 12.16. Found : C, 46.87; H, 2.67; N, 12.15%.

*Synthesis of bis-azido-(N-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- α -aminonaphthalene)cadmium(II) $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(N_3)_2]$ (**5**) :*

N-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]- α -aminonaphthalene (112.1 mg, 0.48 mmol) in MeOH (15 ml) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution (20 ml) of $Cd(OAc)_2$ (129.4 mg, 0.49 mmol) at room temperature and stirred for 50 min. To the orange yellow solution, 10 ml methanolic solution of NaN_3 (65.1 mg, 1.00 mmol) was added dropwise in stirring condition and stirred for 2.5 h. A yellow precipitate separated out. The precipitate was collected by filtration and dissolved in DMF and kept in a beaker with a few drops of methanol for crystallization. After few days yellowish brown crystal was obtained on the inner wall of the beaker. The yield was 136.5 mg (66%).

The β -isomer was prepared following the same procedure. The yield was 68%. The yield was 70%. Microanalytical data : Anal. Calcd. $C_{16}H_{12}N_8Cd$ (**5**) : C, 44.82; H, 2.80; N, 26.14. Found : C, 44.90; H, 2.76; N, 26.20%. $C_{16}H_{12}N_8Cd$ (**6**) : C, 44.82; H, 2.80; N, 26.14. Found : C, 44.87; H, 2.77; N, 26.1.

*X-Ray crystal structure analysis of $[Cd(\beta\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]_n$ (**4**) :*

The crystals were grown by slow evaporation of the reaction mixture in methanol over a week. Data were collected by Enraf-Nonius CAD-4 diffractometer using fine-focus sealed graphite-monochromatized $Mo\ K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.70930$ Å) at 293(2) K (with dimensions $0.225 \times 0.20 \times 0.15$ mm³). Diffractions were recorded with 2θ in the range $4.60 \leq 2\theta \leq 49.86^\circ$. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters are given in Table 1. Reflection data were recorded using the ψ and ω scan techniques. Data were corrected for L_p and an empirical absorption correction in the $h\ k\ l$ range : $0 \leq h \leq 12$; $0 \leq k \leq 12$; $-18 \leq l \leq 18$. Data reduction was carried out using Maxus Nonius software. The structure was solved by the direct method using SHELXS-97²³ and successive difference Fourier syntheses. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using the riding model. The molecular graphics were carried out using ORTEP-3 for Windows²⁴ and PLATON-99²⁵ programs. The residual electron density is in the range 0.924 and -0.689 eÅ⁻³.

Table 1. Summarised crystallography data of [Cd(β -NaiPy)-(SCN)₂]_n (4)

Crystallographic parameter :	
Empirical formula	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂ Cd
Formula weight	460.84
Crystal system	P21/n
Space group	Monoclinic
Unit cell dimensions :	
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.5750(14)
<i>b</i> (Å)	10.7460(12)
<i>c</i> (Å)	15.432(2)
β (°)	91.868(11)
Volume (Å ³)	1752.7(4)
Z	4
ρ_{calcd} (mg m ⁻³)	1.746
<i>F</i> (000)	912
Crystal size (nm)	0.225 × 0.20 × 0.15
<i>T</i> (K)	293(2)
λ (Å)	0.70930
μ (M _o -K α) mm ⁻¹	1.492
Uniq data	2576
Refined parameters	266
R ^a	0.0487
wR ^b	0.1048
GOF ^c	1.033

$$^a R = \frac{\sum ||F_o| - |F_c||}{\sum |F_o|}$$

$$^b wR2 = \frac{[\sum (w|F_o|^2 - |F_c|^2)^2]}{\sum w(|F_o|)^2}^{1/2}$$

$$W = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0396P)^2 + 6.9978P], P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$$

^cGOF (Goodness of fit) is defined as $[\sum (F_o - F_c)/(n_o - n_v)]^{1/2}$ where n_o and n_v denote the number of data and variables, respectively.

Computational methods :

Monomeric unit of [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂]_n (4) is fragmented and is optimized using the Gaussian03 (G03)²⁶ software package running under Windows. The Becke's three-parameter hybrid exchange functional and the Lee-Yang-Parr nonlocal correlation functional (B3LYP)²⁷ was used throughout. Elements except cadmium were assigned a 6-31G* basis set in our calculations. For cadmium the Los Alamos effective core potential plus double zeta (LanL2DZ)²⁸ basis set was employed. Gas-phase optimization was carried out from the geometry obtained from the crystal structure without any symmetry constraints. In all cases, vibrational frequencies were calculated to ensure that optimized geometries represented local minima. GaussSum²⁹ was used to calculate the fractional contri-

butions of various groups to each molecular orbital. This is done using Mulliken population analysis.

Results and discussion

The synthesis and formulation :

N-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]- α (or β)-aminonaphthalene, (α -NaiPy (1), β -NaiPy (2)) are used in this work. They are N(pyridine), N(imine) bidentate chelator (Scheme 1).

The complexes bis-thiocyanato-*N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- α -/ β -aminonaphthalene)cadmium(II), [Cd(α -/ β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (3/4) and bis-azido-*N*-[(2-pyridyl)methylidene]- α -aminonaphthalene)cadmium(II), [Cd(α -/ β -NaiPy)(N₃)₂]_n (5/6) were synthesized by reacting methanolic solution of ligands (1 or 2) and Cd(OAc)₂ in equimolar quantities followed by the addition of two equivalent of NH₄SCN or NaN₃ respectively to the same reaction mixture. The complexes 3 and 4 were collected by slow evaporation of solvent where as 5 and 6 precipitated out from the reaction mixture. Microanalytical data support the composition of the complexes. The complexes are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents like MeOH, EtOH, MeCN, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂ while soluble in DMF and DMSO. Molar conductance measurements suggest that the compounds are non-conducting in DMF.

Molecular structure of [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂]_n (4) :

For exact definition of the coordination sphere, a single-crystal X-ray diffraction study was made. An ORTEP diagram with the atom numbering scheme of one of the complexes, [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂]_n (4) is shown in Fig. 1. Selected bond distances and bond angles relevant to the Cd coordination sphere are given in Table 2. The crystal lattice consists of thiocyanato bridged 2-D polymer. The coordination polyhedron around cadmium is best described as distorted octahedral with a CdN₄S₂ chromophore. β -NaiPy binds in a chelating fashion, [Cd(-N=C-C=N-)] and the chelate angle is 70.7(2)°. The Cd-N(py) bond length [Cd(1)-N(1), 2.346(6) Å] is shortened by 0.04 Å compared to Cd-N(naphthyl) distance [Cd(1)-N(2), 2.389(6) Å]. The atomic arrangements Cd(1), N(1), C(2), C(5), N(2) constitute a plane (mean deviation <0.07 Å) and the pendant naphthyl ring makes a dihedral 36.9(3)° with the plane. This suggests significant structural distortion. The Cd^{II} ions are alternately linked by two N coordination from two SCN [Cd(1)-N(3), 2.297(7) Å; Cd-N(4),

Scheme 1. Synthetic outline : [Cd(α -NaiPy)(SCN)₂]_n (3); [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂]_n (4); [Cd(α -NaiPy)(N₃)₂]_n (5); [Cd(β -NaiPy)(N₃)₂]_n (6).

Fig. 1. ORTEP structure of [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂]_n (4) showing SCN bridging in 2-D polymer.

2.305(7) Å) and two S coordination from other two SCN [Cd(1)-S(1), 2.684(2) Å; Cd(1)-S(2), 2.800(2) Å]. The Cd(1)-S(1)-C(17) and Cd(1)-S(2)-C(18) angles are 102.1(3)° and 105.7(3)°, respectively. The Cd(1)-N(3)-C(18) and Cd(1)-N(4)-C(17) angles are 168.3(7)° (symmetry : 1/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z) and 156.7(7)° (symmetry :

Table 2. Bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) of [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (4)

Bond length (Å)		Bond angle (°)	
Cd(1)-N(1)	2.346(6)	N(1)-Cd(1)-N(3)	87.7(2)
Cd(1)-N(2)	2.389(6)	N(4)-Cd(1)-N(1)	94.5(2)
Cd(1)-N(3)	2.297(7)	N(3)-Cd(1)-N(2)	158.4(2)
Cd(1)-N(4)	2.305(7)	N(4)-Cd(1)-N(2)	87.4(3)
Cd(1)-S(1)	2.684(2)	N(2)-Cd(1)-N(1)	70.7(2)
Cd(1)-S(2)	2.800(2)	N(3)-Cd(1)-S(1)	89.30(19)
C(17)-S(1)	1.640(9)	N(4)-Cd(1)-S(1)	91.61(17)
C(18)-S(2)	1.643(8)	N(1)-Cd(1)-S(1)	173.52(14)
		N(2)-Cd(1)-S(1)	111.87(17)
		N(3)-Cd(1)-S(2)	95.07(19)
		N(4)-Cd(1)-S(2)	166.4(2)
		N(1)-Cd(1)-S(2)	92.77(14)
		N(2)-Cd(1)-S(2)	84.12(16)
		S(1)-Cd(1)-S(2)	81.74(7)

-x, -y, 1-z), respectively. The bridging (Cd)-N-C-S-(Cd) is almost linear (~179°). The N-C and C-S distances lie in the reported range of bridged SCN complexes in different metal complexes of d¹⁰ electronic configuration^{30,31}. The *trans* angles, N(2)-Cd(1)-N(3), 158.4(2); N(1)-Cd(1)-S(1), 173.52(14); N(4)-Cd(1)-S(2), 166.4(2)°, deviate significantly from linearity. The molecular structure determination shows that there are two types of bridging SCN groups about Cd^{II} centre. A dimer is formed by doubly bridging to constitute repeating 'Cd(SCN)₂Cd' motif. Each Cd centre in this motif is bonded with two SCN groups which are eligible to bind neighbouring 'Cd(SCN)₂Cd' motif to develop 2D-polymer.

DFT calculation has been performed for this compound. The optimized structure of the molecule is developed using Gaussian 03 analyses package. The structural agreement has been observed from the comparison of bond distances and angles between calculated and X-ray determined structures. The bond lengths in theoretically generated molecules are elongated by 0.01–0.04 Å than that of experimental structures.

Spectral characterization :

Infrared and UV-Visible spectra :

The vibration bands are assigned on comparing with the free ligand data^{16–18}. The $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{N}_3)$ appears as a sharp strong single band at 2034–2057 cm⁻¹ for 5 and 6³² and $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{SCN})$ appears as a sharp doublet at 2061–2095 and

2110–2115 cm⁻¹ for 3 and 4^{16,17,30,31}. The complexes exhibit very strong vibration at 1590–1605 cm⁻¹ and support the presence of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ which is red shifted by 15–30 cm⁻¹ compared to free ligand value (1620 cm⁻¹). Using optimized geometry generated by Gauss-03 computation programme vibrational frequencies are calculated and have been compared with experimental data. Theoretical frequencies are red shifted by 15–30 cm⁻¹. The calculated $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{SCN})$ of 4 are 2067 and 2097 cm⁻¹ and experimental data show 2095 and 2112 cm⁻¹; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of coordinated ligand appears at 1590 cm⁻¹ and calculated spectrum shows strong stretch at 1605 cm⁻¹.

The electronic spectra in DMF solution of [Cd(NaiPy)(X)₂]_n show intense absorption (Fig. 2) bands in the UV region 330–350 nm, 270–280 nm ($\epsilon \sim 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of the complexes where [Cd(α -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (3), [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (4), [Cd(α -NaiPy)(N₃)₂] (5) and [Cd(β -NaiPy)(N₃)₂] (6) in DMF.

(Table 3). These transitions may be assigned to intraligand charge transfer ($n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$) transitions. Theoretically generated structure of 4 is used to calculate composition and energy of some molecular functions. These are used to explain the electronic properties of the complex and are extended to generalize the spectral properties of similar complexes. The orbital energies along with contributions from the ligands and metal are given in *Supplementary materials*. Fig. 3 depicts the selected occupied and unoccupied frontier orbitals with their energy and composition. The HOMO-2, HOMO-1 are constituted by >60% contribution from β -NaiPy while HOMO is made up of only SCN group (93%). LUMO+1, LUMO+2 are composed of only from β -NaiPy (99%) function while

Table 3. UV-Vis^a and fluorescence^a and quantum yield data

Compd.	UV-Vis spectral data λ_{\max} (e, M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Fluorescence spectral data		Quantum yield (ϕ)	τ_f (ns)	$k_f \times 10^{-9}$	$k_{nr} \times 10^{-9}$
		λ_{ex}	λ_{em}				
[Cd(α -NaiPy)(SCN) ₂] (3)	336 (11936); 269 (33202)	336	433	0.47426	6.643	0.071391	0.079147
[Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN) ₂] (4)	349 (2687); 282 (7362); 273 (7413)	349	408	0.00579	11.020	0.0005254	0.0902187
[Cd(α -NaiPy)(N ₃) ₂] (5)	337 (8324); 268 (10261)	336	433	0.12318	4.680	0.026318	0.187338
[Cd(β -NaiPy)(N ₃) ₂] (6)	347 (4659); 282 (13750); 272 (14117)	349	410	0.00578	3.444	0.001678	0.288683

^aThe spectra were recorded in DMF.

Fig. 3. Some selected MOs of [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (4) in gas phase with their composition and energy.

LUMO is impregnated with 87% SCN contribution. Thus HOMO→LUMO, the conventional transition, may not be considered as major transition rather HOMO-2/1→LUMO and/or HOMO-2/1→LUMO+2/1 are acceptable transitions. However, the transitions are either ligand-to-ligand or intraligand charge transfer transitions. This is indeed observed.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra are recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ solu-

tion. Data are given in Table 4. The assignment has been made on the basis of spin-spin interaction, and on comparing with free ligand values¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In the complexes, 3-6, the proton signals of coordinated ligand α/β -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine are shifted to downfield by 0.10–0.25 ppm compared to free ligand value. Most down field singlet is assigned to -HC=N- (7H) (8.89–8.92 ppm). Pyridyl proton 6-H appears at 8.70–8.78 ppm. Other pyridyl protons (3-H to 5-H) appear at 7.9–8.2 ppm and

Table 4. ¹H NMR spectral data of the complexes in DMSO-*d*₆

Compd.	(δ) ppm (J, Hz)							
	3-H ^d	4-H ^t	5-H ^m	6-H ^d	7-H ^s	8/9,10,11-H ^m	13,14-H ^m	12,15-H ^d
3	8.23 (7.9)	8.09 (7.5)	8.01	8.72 (3.6)	8.88	7.92–8.09	7.54	7.64 (8.5)
4	8.21 (7.8)	8.10 (7.5)	8.0	8.76 (3.5)	8.89	7.95–8.04	7.55	7.65 (8.6)
5	8.22 (7.9)	8.09 (7.6)	8.02	8.73 (3.6)	8.87	7.96–8.05	7.57	7.66
6	9.20 (7.8)	8.11 (7.4)	7.99	8.74 (3.5)	8.90	7.91–8.2	7.55	7.66

Fig. 4. Fluorescence spectra of the complexes where [Cd(α -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (3), [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (4), [Cd(α -NaiPy)(N₃)₂] (5) and [Cd(β -NaiPy)(N₃)₂] (6) in DMF.

naphthyl protons (8-H to 15-H) exhibit resonance at upper field side, 7.5–8.1 ppm. This, in fact, supports the structural aspect of these complexes.

Photoluminescence spectra :

The photoluminescence properties of Cd^{II}-complexes (3, 4, 5 and 6) were studied at room temperature (298 K) (Fig. 4). Free ligands exhibit photoluminescence with emission at 431 and 406 nm for α -NaiPy and β -NaiPy respectively at 298 K upon excitation at 340 nm. These emissions are neither metal-to-ligand charge transfer nor ligand-to-metal charge transfer in nature, because it is difficult to oxidize or reduce Cd^{II} ions due to d¹⁰ configuration. Thus, the emission is assigned to the intraligand π --- π^* emission i.e. it may belong to intraligand charge transfer (ILCT) or ligand-to-ligand charge transfer (LLCT)

Fig. 5. Single exponential of [Cd(α -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (3) and bi-exponential [Cd(β -NaiPy)(SCN)₂] (4), [Cd(α -NaiPy)(N₃)₂] (5) and [Cd(β -NaiPy)(N₃)₂] (6) decay profile (•) and fitting curve (----) in DMF solution. Excitation is carried out at 370 nm.

transitions. DFT calculation (Fig. 3) also supports this conjecture. Zn^{II} ¹⁶ and Pd^{II} ¹⁹ complexes also show high emission. It is interesting to note that Cd^{II} complexes show higher intensity than Zn^{II} complexes although Cd^{II} is heavier than Zn^{II} . This is supported from their calculated quantum yield (Table 3) with reference to carbazole laser dye. It has been reported that the metal ions can enhance or quench the fluorescence emission of pyridine containing compounds³³. In the absence of metal ions the fluorescence of ligand is probably quenched by the occurrence of photoinduced electron transfer (PET) process due to the presence of a lone pair of nitrogen atoms. Such a PET process is prevented by the complexation of L with metal ions; thus the fluorescence intensity may be greatly enhanced by the coordination of Cd^{II} . Quantum yields (ϕ), in general, are higher for the complexes of α -NaiPy than β -NaiPy (Table 3). The difference of photoluminescence intensity between free ligands and the complexes may be interpreted in terms of free ligand impurity or free ligand produced as a result of photodissociation. This possibility is not ruled out³⁴ but we have done ¹H NMR spectra of $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]_n$ (3) after irradiation for 5 min in $CDCl_3$ solution. The spectra of nonirradiated and irradiated complexes are identical from all respect. Besides, luminescence intensity remains unchanged upon repetitive irradiation which supports fairly stable C=N bond.

Life time data of the complexes are taken in DMF solution (Fig. 5). The fluorescence decay curve was deconvoluted with respect to the lamp profile. The observed fluorescence decay fits nicely with single exponential decay profile for $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]$ (3), and bi-exponential decay profile for $[Cd(\beta\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]$ (4), $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(N_3)_2]$ (5) and $[Cd(\beta\text{-NaiPy})(N_3)_2]$ (6). This is supported by goodness-of-fit (χ^2) data in the regression analyses. Radiative and non-radiative rate constants (k_r and k_{nr}) are calculated and data show usual higher k_{nr} value than k_r .

Conclusion :

N-[(2-Pyridyl)methylidene]- α (or β)-aminonaphthalene (α - or β -NaiPy) (α/β -NaiPy) belongs to diimine and serve as N(pyridine), N(imine) chelating agent. Cadmium(II)-azido and thiocyanato complexes of NaiPy are described. The structural study reveals that there are two types of bridging SCN groups about Cd^{II} centre. A dimer is

formed by SCN bridging to form ' $Cd(SCN)_2Cd$ ' motif which serves as repeating unit. Each Cd centre is bonded with two SCN groups which are eligible to bind neighbouring ' $Cd(SCN)_2Cd$ ' motif to develop 2D-polymer. The complexes are noticeably luminescent and dynamics of the complexes show single exponential decay profile for $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]$ (3), and bi-exponential decay profile for $[Cd(\beta\text{-NaiPy})(SCN)_2]$ (4), $[Cd(\alpha\text{-NaiPy})(N_3)_2]$ (5) and $[Cd(\beta\text{-NaiPy})(N_3)_2]$ (6).

Supplementary material :

Crystallographic data for the structure have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC No. 726658. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (*E-mail* : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www:http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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